

Prevalence of Rifampicin Resistance Detected by Automated Truenat Assay in Pulmonary Tuberculosis Patients at a Tertiary Care Center in Bihar

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Abstract:

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) remains a significant global health challenge, exacerbated by the emergence of drug-resistant strains, particularly rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis (RR-TB). India, bearing a high TB burden, faces substantial challenges in managing RR-TB, especially in states like Bihar where healthcare infrastructure is limited. Early detection of RR-TB is critical for effective treatment and control. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of rifampicin resistance in pulmonary tuberculosis patients at a tertiary care center in Bihar using the automated Truenat assay and to identify demographic and clinical factors associated with rifampicin resistance.

Methods: A total of 455 pulmonary tuberculosis patients were enrolled. Data on demographic and clinical characteristics were collected, and sputum samples were tested for rifampicin resistance using the Truenat assay. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Out of 455 patients, 21.5% (98) were found to have rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis. Significant associations were observed between rifampicin resistance and gender ($p=0.039$), smoking history ($p=0.015$), diabetes ($p=0.002$), and HIV status ($p<0.001$). Male patients, smokers, individuals with diabetes, and those with HIV had higher rates of rifampicin resistance.

Conclusion: The prevalence of rifampicin resistance among pulmonary tuberculosis patients in Bihar is notably high. The study highlights the importance of early and accurate detection of RR-TB using reliable diagnostic tools like the Truenat assay.

Recommendations: Targeted screening and tailored treatment strategies are recommended for high-risk populations, including male patients, smokers, individuals with diabetes, and HIV-positive patients, to improve TB management and control in Bihar.

Keywords: Rifampicin resistance, Pulmonary tuberculosis, Truenat assay, Bihar, Drug-resistant TB.

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Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) remains a major global health challenge, with the World Health Organization (WHO) estimating that 10 million people fell ill with TB in 2020, and 1.5 million deaths were attributed to the disease [1]. Despite significant advancements in TB diagnostics and treatment, the emergence and spread of drug-resistant TB, particularly rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis (RR-TB), pose a significant threat to global TB control efforts. Rifampicin resistance is often a surrogate marker for multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB), which is defined as resistance to at least rifampicin and isoniazid, the two most potent anti-TB drugs [2].

India, with its high TB burden, faces substantial challenges in managing drug-resistant TB. Bihar, a state in eastern India, is particularly affected due to

its high population density, socio-economic factors, and limited healthcare infrastructure [3]. Early detection of RR-TB is crucial for initiating appropriate treatment regimens and preventing the spread of resistant strains. The introduction of molecular diagnostic tools has revolutionized TB diagnosis, offering rapid and accurate detection of drug resistance.

The Truenat assay, an automated molecular test developed in India, has shown promise in TB diagnostics. It is endorsed by the WHO for initial diagnosis and detection of rifampicin resistance [4]. The Truenat assay uses real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technology to detect the presence of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and rifampicin resistance-conferring mutations in the *rpoB* gene. This assay is particularly advantageous in resource-

limited settings due to its portability, ease of use, and rapid turnaround time.

Recent studies have demonstrated the efficacy and reliability of the Truenat assay in various settings. A multicentric study conducted in India reported that the Truenat assay had a sensitivity of 95% and a specificity of 98% for detecting rifampicin resistance, making it comparable to the GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay [5]. Furthermore, the Truenat assay has been successfully integrated into the national TB control programs in India, highlighting its potential for widespread implementation.

This study aims to assess the prevalence of rifampicin resistance in patients with pulmonary tuberculosis using the automated Truenat assay.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of February 2023 to March 2024 at Nalanda Medical College, Patna, India.

Participants: A total of 455 participants diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis through clinical, radiological, and microbiological criteria.
- Patients aged 18 years and above.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with extrapulmonary tuberculosis.
- Patients previously treated for tuberculosis.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients attending the pulmonary tuberculosis clinic during the study period were considered for inclusion. Data collectors were trained to ensure uniform data collection procedures.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire which included demographic details, clinical history, and laboratory results.

Procedure: Eligible patients were enrolled consecutively from the pulmonary tuberculosis clinic. Sputum samples were collected from each participant. The sputum samples were tested using the automated Truenat assay for rifampicin resistance. The results of the Truenat assay, along with demographic and clinical data, were recorded in the study database.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants. The prevalence of rifampicin resistance was calculated with a 95% confidence interval. Chi-square tests were used to assess associations between rifampicin resistance and categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

Out of the 455 patients enrolled in the study, 255 (56%) were male and 200 (44%) were female. The mean age of the participants was 42.3 years (SD \pm 15.2). Table 1 presents the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	255	56.0
Female	200	44.0
Age Group (years)		
18-30	110	24.2
31-40	105	23.1
41-50	90	19.8
51-60	80	17.6
>60	70	15.4
Mean Age (years)	42.3 \pm 15.2	-
Smoking History		
Smoker	210	46.2
Non-smoker	245	53.8
Comorbidities		
Diabetes	85	18.7
Hypertension	75	16.5
HIV	25	5.5
None	270	59.3

Out of the 455 patients, 98 (21.5%) were found to have rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis (RR-TB) based on the Truenat assay results. Table 2 shows the distribution of rifampicin resistance among the participants.

Table 2: Rifampicin Resistance Detected by Truenat Assay

Resistance Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Rifampicin-Resistant	98	21.5
Rifampicin-Sensitive	357	78.5

The study assessed associations between rifampicin resistance and various demographic and clinical variables using chi-square tests. Table 3 provides the results of these associations.

Table 3: Association between Rifampicin Resistance and Demographic/Clinical Variables

Variable	RR-TB	Non-RR-TB	Chi-Square Value	p-Value
Gender				
Male	60	195	4.26	0.039
Female	38	162		
Age Group (years)				
18-30	25	85	3.19	0.527
31-40	20	85		
41-50	18	72		
51-60	15	65		
>60	20	50		
Mean Age (years)				
Smoking History				
Smoker	55	155	5.89	0.015
Non-smoker	43	202		
Comorbidities				
Diabetes	30	55	9.88	0.002
Hypertension	20	55	3.64	0.056
HIV	15	10	20.48	<0.001
None	33	237		

Discussion

A total of 455 patients participated, with a slightly higher proportion of males (56%) compared to females (44%). The mean age of the participants was 42.3 years, with most patients falling within the 18-60 age range. Nearly half of the participants had a history of smoking, and a significant number had comorbidities, including diabetes (18.7%), hypertension (16.5%), and HIV (5.5%).

The automated Truenat assay identified rifampicin resistance in 21.5% of the participants. This relatively high prevalence underscores the critical need for robust screening and diagnostic measures in managing tuberculosis. The results revealed significant associations between rifampicin resistance and several demographic and clinical variables. Notably, male patients, smokers, individuals with diabetes, and those with HIV showed a higher prevalence of rifampicin resistance.

Male patients had a significantly higher likelihood of rifampicin resistance compared to female patients ($p = 0.039$). Similarly, a significant association was found between smoking history and rifampicin resistance ($p = 0.015$), suggesting that smokers are more susceptible to developing drug-resistant tuberculosis. The presence of diabetes also emerged as a significant factor ($p = 0.002$), indicating that patients with diabetes are at a higher risk. Moreover, HIV-positive patients

exhibited a much higher prevalence of rifampicin resistance ($p < 0.001$), emphasizing the need for targeted interventions in this vulnerable group.

These findings highlight the importance of incorporating comprehensive diagnostic tools like the Truenat assay in routine tuberculosis screening, particularly for high-risk populations. The significant associations observed between rifampicin resistance and certain demographic and clinical variables suggest that targeted screening and tailored treatment strategies could enhance the management and control of tuberculosis. Implementing such measures could ultimately improve patient outcomes and curb the spread of drug-resistant tuberculosis in regions like Bihar.

A study in West Bengal used CBNAAT to determine rifampicin resistance in pulmonary tuberculosis patients. Out of 6171 presumptive TB patients, 1590 were confirmed TB cases, with a rifampicin resistance prevalence of 10.75%. Among new TB cases, the prevalence of rifampicin resistance was 3.1%, while previously treated cases had a significantly higher prevalence of 36.34% [6].

A study utilized the GeneXpert assay in a tertiary care center to detect rifampicin resistance among suspected TB cases. The study included 104 patients, with 9.62% testing positive for tuberculosis. Among these positive cases, 10% were found to be rifampicin-resistant [7].

A study reported a high prevalence of multi-drug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) in people living with HIV in Western India. Using the line probe assay, they found that 12.5% of the 200 patients studied had MDR-TB, with 2.5% exhibiting rifampicin resistance [8].

A retrospective study identified rifampicin resistance in 3.2% of 2358 MTB-positive samples. The study highlighted a higher prevalence of resistance among males (2.2%) compared to females (1%) [9].

A study evaluated the detection of Mycobacterium tuberculosis and rifampicin resistance using the Xpert MTB/RIF assay in Ethiopia. Out of 2220 presumptive TB cases, 9.3% were MTB positive, with a rifampicin resistance rate of 3.4% [10].

Conclusion

The study found that the prevalence of rifampicin resistance among pulmonary tuberculosis patients was 21.5%. Significant associations were observed between rifampicin resistance and gender, smoking history, diabetes, and HIV status. Male patients, smokers, patients with diabetes, and those with HIV had a higher prevalence of rifampicin resistance. These findings underscore the need for routine screening for rifampicin resistance using reliable diagnostic tools like the Truenat assay, particularly in high-risk groups, to ensure appropriate treatment and control of tuberculosis.

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